

METHOD OF GLASSREINFORCED PLASTICS WINDING FROM VIRGIN GLASSMONOFILAMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The paper discusses specific features of the process that combines spinning of glassfibres from spinneret with their coating with polymer binders and simultaneous winding of glassfibrereinforced plastic (GFRP) structural elements. The paper demonstrates the possibility of full realization of the fibres initial strength and manufacturing of materials with the properties significantly surpassing those of the analogous GFRP.

INTRODUCTION

An interesting production method of advanced glassfibrereinforced plastics (GFRP) suggested by A.K. Burov and G.D. Andreevskaya [1] is a one-stage SVAM process that combines spinning of glassfibres from spinneret with their coating with polymer binders and orientation in glueing medium that allows to produce the so-called glass-ply, i.e. the unwoven unidirectional or crossplied prepreg which can be remanufactured into articles by hot pressing or winding with hot curing of the wound articles.

The advantages of this method are determined by the absence of the intermediary stages in processing of glassfibres that allows to use fibres with various diameters (from 5-7 to 150-200 mkm) and preserve their initial strength. In case of the one-stage process it is also possible not to use technological sizes which reduces water resistance and the dielectrical properties of materials.

A.K. Burov foresaw the possibility of producing in the course of spinning not only the glass-ply, but ready-to-use filament wound articles. For this it is necessary, apart from coating the fibre with binders, to arrange the thread forming, its pre-tension and required orientation on the technological mandrel in the way that satisfies the structural requirements for the ready article. The basic scheme of the method is shown at Fig.1.

The basic technological feature of this process is high speed of GFRP winding, which is determined by conditions of fibres spinning. Therefore for production of fibres with widely spread diameters of 10-15 mkm the speed reaches dozens and hundreds meters per minute which is one-two orders higher than the speed of thread winding in the traditional processes. It is evident that in case under discussion the conditions for fibre spinning, forming and tension as well as for winding of the articles are very specific and required special research.

EXPERIMENTS

In our experiments we used the standard 200-dies platinum-rhodium spinnerets for manufacturing of the industrial type glass fibre with the dies diametre 1,2; 1,4; 1,7 and 2,1 mm. The spinneret was installed into the thermoinsulating enclosure and connected to the furnace transformer. Spinning of glassfibres (alumoborosilicate composition type "E") was performed at the usual technical parameters-level of liquid glass - 100 mm, spinneret plate temperature - 1180°C that were maintained automatically.

The experimental installation was designed in such a way that the spinneret together with the furnace were mounted on the mobile carriage that allowed to move it at different speed along the mandrel axis mounted on the winding installation. The fibres pulled out of the spinneret were then collected into thread on the roller-applicator onto which the solvent or melt epoxy binder was fed in predetermined quantities. The thread pretension was performed on the kinking (pretension) rollers and measured by means of strain gauges. The winding installation ensured the fair change of the mandrel rotation speed from 10 to 1000 m/min. The speed of the longitudinal movement of the carriage with the spinneret ensured the necessary winding pitch from 0,5 to 10 mm/turn, that allowed to produce impregnated strands, glass-plyes or ring samples.

For helicoidal cross-plyed or orbital (polar) winding we used special leading heads with the screw or chain drive that ensured high speed of the reciprocating movement of the thread along the mandrel, the spinneret, the applicators and the pretension rollers being at the stationary state. After curing of the binder the wound samples were taken from the mandrels and tested under different loading conditions on the universal testing machines "Reinstein" -250 and 10 000 kg and "Instron" -500 kg. Below we shall discuss the impact of the basic factors constituting the process.

Fig.1. Basic scheme of the method of the glassfibre-reinforced plastics articles winding from virgin monofilaments; 1. Spinneret; 2. Roller-applicator; 3. Mandrel; 4. Pretension rollers; 5. Leading head.

Fig.2. Glassfibres strength correlation to their diameter.

Undamaged fibres: 1. Thomas' data; 2-5 Our data for diameters of dies 1,2; 1,4; 1,7 and 2,1 mm respectively. Ready-to-use threads: 6. Our data; 7. Griffith's data.

CONDITIONS OF FIBRES SPINNING

The essential parameter for glass fibres spinning process is the spinneret discharge - Q , i.e. the quantity of liquid glass flowing out per time unit. This parameter depends on the design of the spinneret (diameter of dies, liquid glass level), glass composition and melt temperature. At constant technological parameters the spinneret discharge remains unaltered, in our experiments for the spinnerets with different dies diameters it varied from 15 to 60 g/min. Discharge does not depend on winding speed, and this allows to calculate the speed necessary for obtaining fibres of the desired diameter.

Dispersion of diameters of glassfibres pulled out from multidiered spinnerets is determined by nonuniformity of the temperature field of the spinneret plate and by the fluctuating character of the fibres formation process caused by the surface tension of melt glass. Distribution of glassfibres diameters is usually monomodal. Variation coefficient of the glassfibres diameter in a bundle and along a monofilament fibre is usually 10-15% and has no correlation to fibres diameters.

Fig.2 shows the correlation of elementary glass fibres strength and their diameters. Curves 1-5 characterize strength of the undamaged samples that were produced and tested in accordance with methods developed by W.Thomas and ourselves. They have high initial strength (up to 3,8 GPa) at low dispersion, and a considerably lower influence of the diameter as compared to classical correlations (for example, curves 6 and 7 obtained by ourselves and by A. Griffith respectively [2] that reflect degree of fibres damaging during their withdrawal from the thread, preparing and testing the samples. Various initial strength of fibres pulled out from spinnerets with dies diametres from 1,2 to 2,1 mm (curves 2-5) is accounted for by different degree of homogenization of liquid glass that is correlated to time of its staying in the spinneret.

CONDITIONS OF COATING THE SURFACE OF MONOFILAMENTS WITH BINDER

In contrast to impregnation of ready threads when the binder has to penetrate into multifilamentary thread consolidated by size, in case under discussion the binder is coated on each fibre since they get into the binder separately. The binder-coating devices - motionless and rotating roller applicators are similar to the industrial devices for size coating (diameter 70-100 mm, embracing angle 60 - 90°). Tests were made on sample liquids with viscosity from 20 to 200 c η that were the combination of epoxy resin ED-20 and active dilute DEG-1. In some cases melts of resins with temperature up to 90°C were used. First of all we wanted to determine the "fibre rapture criteria", i.e. at what minimal diameter it would be possible to stably perform winding depending on the viscosity of the binder. To this end we fairly increased the rotation speed of the mandrel and fixed it at the moment of rapture of fibers on the roller-applicator. Then we calculated fiber diameters based on the known discharge and winding speed. Fig. 3 shows that for winding of fibres with wide-spread diameters of 10-15 mkm it is possible to use binders with viscosity of approx. 100 c η wich does not exceed the usual criteria of requirements to the binder viscosity at "wet" filament winding. For fibres with larger diameters it is possible to apply binders with higher viscosity. In case it is necessary to additionally decrease viscosity it is convenient to use roller-applicators with local heating of the coating zone. In this case binder heating is a short-time process.

One of the simplest ways to decrease viscosity is to add high volatile solvents. Thus, adding of 10% alckohol-aceton mixture to epoxy-diane binder EDT-10 at room temperature decreases its viscosity from 3500 to 90 c η . We studied solvent content in

the wound structure for different concentration of solvents, their types, speed of rotation and shelf life at room and elevated temperatures. The main part of the solvent is evaporated right during winding, volatile content being 1-3%. The thickness of the sample does not have any considerable impact. The higher the winding speed is, the less solvent is left in the sample. Exposition of the wound samples at room temperature is loweffective, whereas at elevated temperature evaporation of the solvent is quite active. In this case application of volatile solvents in glassfibreplastics from elementary fibres is questionable since there is a chance for inflammation of the solvent. However our long experimental experience gives ground for optimism.

We also studied the balance of binder consumption during elementary fibres winding depending on the binder viscosity η , fed liquid quantity - G , and winding speed - W . number of fibres in the thread - N . Thus we determined the amount of binder - q , that was taken by the thread from the roller-applicator, and its losses during contact with the pretension rollers and from centrifugal throwoff- R . Fig. 4 shows that parametres q and R increase with the rise of η and W . Influence of the other factors (G and N) is considerably less significant.

Losses of binder R is an essentially important question. At high feed G and high viscosity the losses can equal 100%, however, optimization of parameters allows to decrease them to 20-40%. Considerable part of losses can then be successfully utilized. One has to stress that in spite of the high winding speed the fibrous material is impregnated quite uniformly. This manifests itself in its low porosity (1-3%) and specific transparency related evidently to absence of sizes. Finishing agents improving adhesive interaction of the components can be introduced directly into the binder. Matrix content in a composite usually constitutes 18-22% of the total weight (or 25-35% by volume) and is determined in the process of forming by compactness of fibres packing that is correlated to their diameter, binder viscosity and level of tension.

Fig. 3. Dependence of fibres minimum diameter d_f on binder viscosity ("fibre rapture criteria"); W - winding speed.

Fig. 4. Dependence of amount q and losses of binder R on binder viscosity η .

CONDITIONS FOR CREATING PRETENSION DURING GFRP WINDING PROCEDURES

Conditions for creating pretension during GFRP winding differ considerably from those set up for ready-to-use threads winding. Initial pretension of GFRP is determined by their production parameters. Additional pretension is created at forming the thread on the roller-applicator and on the tension rollers and depends on the binder viscosity, speed of the bundle, diameters of the rollers and value of the friction surface. Fig. 5 shows correlation of pretension and bundle speed. Curve 1 shows the initial tension of fibres, its value is approximately 100 g and it changes very insignificantly with the speed increase. Curves 2 and 3 show respectively changes of pretension on the roller-applicator and the tension rollers. In both cases the bundle tension rises significantly with the increase of the binder viscosity and winding speed. At the same time the value of pretension does not depend on the quantity of resin fed to the roller-applicator. Such correlation is typical for liquid friction conditions. Correlation of bundle pretension - P to surface friction is usually a linear function in half-logorythmic coordinates. Our tests showed some deviation caused by liquid friction. Thus, as one should have supposed, when the binder is coated on monofilaments and the bundle moves along the tension rollers there exists half-liquid friction (coating friction), whose value is correlated to movement speed and viscosity of the liquid as well as to the surface friction.

During bundle forming on the roller-applicator and during its further movement along the tension rollers only part of fibres contact surface of friction which is the reason of nonuniformity of fibres pretension. This manifests itself in nonlinear character of the function of pretension versus fibres number. Nonuniformity of fibres within the bundle and high winding speed that causes dynamic loads significantly influence maximum value of pretension, when the thread is ruptured - F . Fig. 6 shows comparison of F values obtained under static and dynamic conditions for bundles containing different fibres number. Evidently maximum value of pretension during GFRP winding cannot exceed 20% of the filament strength under static conditions. To decrease dynamic loads it is expedient to use well balanced mandrels. Diminishing of nonuniformity of fibres tension becomes especially important with the increase of their diameter over 50 mkm. For this case we designed multigrooved roller-applicators that allow to perform tension of each separate fibre (or a group of fibres).

Fig.5. Correlation of pretension P and winding speed W ; d_f - fibres diameter;

Fig.6. Rapture load of the thread F versus number of fibres N under dynamic winding conditions (1) and static loading (2).

FORMING OF ARTICLES BY WINDING OF MONOFILAMENTS

It was mentioned above that the main peculiarity of articles forming by winding of filaments is the high speed of the bundle movement. In case of thin fibres it exceeds the speed for ready-to-use threads by factor of 10-15. Only for thick fibres the winding speed decreases to 10-30 m/min. It is specifically essential to keep the winding speed constant to ensure stability of fibres spinning. In those cases when this condition is difficult to be satisfied one has to introduce a special compensation device into the scheme of the technological process. Monofilaments winding is performed with the single initial filament, that is why the winding pitch and thickness of the wound layer are very small. This allows to obtain smooth surface of the article and high accuracy in the required sizes.

Industrial type spinneret output is 100-400 kg/per day. Winding should be performed without breaks since heating and cooling of the spinneret require considerable amount of time. Winding process can be fully automated. Setting-up of thread to the next mandrel can be performed in the same way as for spinning the glass fibres by turn of the revolving mechanism, or else with the help of the leading head moving the wound thread on to the coaxially placed neighbouring mandrel.

Experimental tests showed that the easiest type of winding is the radial one with the transverse orientation of fibres to the mandrel axis. It is the most effective for strengthening shells, metal layners, super fly-wheels in which radial loads usually occur. Cross-ply winding for production of thin glass fibres presents certain difficulties caused by necessity to ensure high speed of the longitudinal movement of the leading head. Maximum angle of the crossed plies obtained in our experiments was 75° to the mandrel axis. At spinning speed of 400 m/min (fibres diameter 20 μ m) the speed of the leading head was 38 m/min. During cross-ply winding of GFRP based on large diameter fibres the winding angles can be much larger. In some cases it is possible to combine radial winding of glassfibres with longitudinal positioning of glass-plyes or webs which allows to better regulate anisotropic properties of the material in accordance with the operational requirements.

We also tested polar winding. In this case longitudinal layers winding was performed by the leading head movement across the short mandrel. Slow step-by-step rotation of the mandrel ensures continuous coating the the fibres placed on it.

REALIZATION OF FIBRES STRENGTH AND PHYSICAL- MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE UNIDIRECTIONAL GFRP

Discussing realization of glassfibres high strength it is expedient firstly to specify the potentialities of the method. During forming of fibres there is created a juvenile, devoid of any thermostresses surface, the preservation of which would allow to produce fibres with strength of 5,0 -7,0 GPa [3]. Hydration of their surface with moisture (or binder) decreases its strength approximately by factor of 2, i.e. to the values shown in Fig. 2. Also one has to take into account that binder curing process in certain cases produces negative impact on fibres strength [4]. However, only within the method that includes glassfibre spinning and preservation of their surface it is possible to seriously consider the issue of significant enhancing of glassfibre properties without changing composition of glass.

In reality tensile strength of thin glassfibres of type "E" composition in unidirectional structures (strands, glass-plyes and ring samples) is 2,9-3,2 GPa, which corresponds to 80 - 100% of the glassfibres initial strength. The higher the initial strength is, the lower the degree of its realization (Fig.7). Glassfibres strength in similar structures wound from

ready-to-use threads does not usually exceed 2,4 MPa.

Table

Physical-Mechanical Properties of the Unidirectional GFRP
with Diameter of 10-12 mkm

Indicators	Monofilament GF	Ready-to-use threads GF
Density, g/sm	1,9 - 2,1	1,9 - 2,1
Tensile strength, GPa	1,5 - 2,0	1,2 - 1,5
Bending strength, GPa	1,9 - 2,2	1,4 - 1,7
Compressive strength, GPa	1,4 - 1,8	1,0 - 1,2
Module of elasticity, GPa	51 - 54	48 - 51
Water absorbion, %	0,05	0,1 - 0,2
Specific volume resistivity, ohm.cm	10	10
Electric strength, kv/mm	35-40	25-30

The table shows physical-mechanical characteristics of the unidirectional GFRP with fibres diameters of 10-20 mkm and modified epoxy binders in comparison to the characteristics of similar materials produced from ready-to-use threads. It can be seen that GFRP based on monofilament glassfibres strength exceeds that of the produced from ready-to-use threads by 15-25%. It is quite interesting that their fracture is of collective character and to a high extent corresponds to the mechanism described by Rosen's pattern [5], i.e. to splitting fibres into the "critical length" sections. It is known that such mechanism yields the highest strength values of composites. Comparing data in the table one has also to note the low water absorbion and high dielectrical qualities of the described glassfibres. This is accounted for by absence of technological sizes.

With the increase of glassfibres diameter up to 50-200 mkm their module of elasticity and glassfibre volume rise by 10 -15%. The former is related to decrease of cooling speed of liquid glass at spinning, the latter is related to the fact that thick fibres more intensively squeeze the binder out of the interglassfibre space during forming of the material. Fig. 8 shows correlations of GFRP strength to increase of diameters. Tensile strength decreases approximately by factor two and is 0,8-1,0 GPa. It corresponds to decrease of fibres initial strength.

GFRP compressive strength changes in a different way. With increase of fibres diameters it rises by 20-30% and reaches 2,0 GPa. The prevailing fracture mechanism in this case is loss of stability in fibres (in comparison to delamination mechanism) [6]. For ring samples the correlation has maximum which depends upon the diameters of the rings.

CONCLUSION

During our research and experimental work we managed to overcome certain difficulties related to combining the processes of thin fibres spinning, their coating with binders and winding of elements of GFRP articles. Among those difficulties are firstly the necessity to decrease binder viscosity and also to cope with high speed of the procedure which becomes possible only during winding radial-strong structural elements. Using of fibres with diameters of 50-200 mkm requires special conditions that ensure uniform fibres pretension, forming and setting of threads.

Having found the way to make use of one-stage process advantages, which allowed to realize the high initial strength of fibres and not to apply technological sizes we produced glassplastics with physical-mechanical properties considerably surpassing any analogues. From technical and economic point of view application of the described winding method can allow to considerably decrease the production costs.

Fig.7. Dependence of fibre strength σ_f in glass plies on initial strength of glass monofilaments σ_i ; 1,2,3,4 - fibres spun from spinnerets with diameters of dies 1,2; 1,4; 1,7 and 2,1 mm; 5 - fibres produced under artificially created nonuniform temperature field on the die; A - strength of monofilaments coated with cured epoxide binder.

Fig.8. Comparative values of tensile and compressive strength of GFRP rings σ/σ_0 versus fibre diameter d_f ; σ_0 tensile = 1,8 GPa; σ_0 compr. = 1,4 GPa.

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